

Drift of alignment after sweep $\rightarrow$

pH 13 solution slightly yellowish.

Pb.: pH 13 solution prepared at DESY
was more yellowish, according to
recollection of experimenter.

pH dependence of Cts of glucose

Prepared solutions of different pH, as measured by Robert Seidel's pH-meter, calibrated in its own buffer solution.

Running solution directly through HPLC.

Beamline par. s.: $h\nu = 850 \text{ eV}$, 3rd H., exit slit = 60 μ

Solution: glucose, 1M + 25 mM NaCl, pH 12,
adjusted with NaOH, 0.8 ml/min., 10°C
 $T \rightarrow 25^\circ\text{C}$

Cts of 1M glucose, pH 12, $h\nu = 850 \text{ eV}$, mar 21_0031

$E_s = 286 / 298 / 0.0250 \text{ V} / 10\text{-ps}$,

$E_n = 10020 \#4$

$p(\text{ch}) = 4.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ eV}$

18:13 changed to pH 13 sample

Cts of 1M glucose, while change from pH 12-13, mar 21_0032

— as #0031 —

#2

Cts of 1M glucose, pH 13

mar 21_0033

Started six minutes after change of sample

— as #0031 —

#6

Switched to pH = 11 ~ 18:33

Cl₂ of 1M glucose, pH=11, h₀=850 eV, mar 21_0034

$E_b = 286 / 298 / 0.025 \text{ eV} / 10 \text{ fps}$, $E_p = 100 \text{ eV}$ #3

Acquisition started 6 mins after switching to pH=11 solution.

Realigned, restarted

Repeat of mar 21_0034

mar 21_0035